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TUWEP:APHP

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the final Data Management Plan (DMP) for the TU Wien Educational Project: Accurately predicting house prices using machine learning project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan

CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Valentin Futterer will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	ames_housing_prices_model.pkl	Other	application/octet-stream	100 - 1000 MB	no
P2	scatter_absolute_error	Images	image/png	100 - 1000 MB	no
P3	scatter_root_squared_error	Images	image/png	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "ames_housing_prices_model.pkl":

The ML model created from the Ames Housing Prices dataset. Is supposed to be used as a benchmark solution for students.

Description for "scatter_absolute_error":

Scatterplot that shows the absolute error of the ames_housing_prices_model.pkl when its used to predict housing prices on the testing dataset.

Description for "scatter_root_squared_error":

Scatterplot that shows the root squared error of the ames_housing_prices_model.pkl when its used to predict housing prices on the testing dataset.

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Ames Housing Prices Training Split	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.82556/1jqa-zp46		no
R2	Ames Housing Prices Validation Split	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.82556/7cm6-bt62		no
R3	Ames Housing Prices Test Split	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.82556/20e7-a615		no

Description for "Ames Housing Prices Training Split":

Training split of the Ames Housing Data Set (~80%). The dataset is free to use for educational purposes and was converted to csv. Original publication <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock.pdf> and dataset in txt format: <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock/AmesHousing.txt>. For the data documentation, see here: <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock/DataDocumentation.txt>

Description for "Ames Housing Prices Validation Split":

Validation split of the Ames Housing Data Set (~10%). The dataset is free to use for educational purposes and was converted to csv. Original publication <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock.pdf> and dataset in txt format: <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock/AmesHousing.txt> For the data documentation, see here: <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock/DataDocumentation.txt>

Description for "Ames Housing Prices Test Split":

Test split of the Ames Housing Data Set (~10%). The dataset is free to use for educational purposes and was converted to csv. Original publication <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock.pdf> and dataset in txt format: <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock/AmesHousing.txt> For the data documentation, see here: <https://jse.amstat.org/v19n3/decock/DataDocumentation.txt>

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The model and graphics were generated with Python 3.10, sklearn 1.1.0 and pickle. The training, test and validation datasets were split beforehand and stored in DBRepo, from where they were loaded over the API. To reuse the model, open the `ames_housing_prices-model` file with pickle and use sklearn on fitting data to try out the model. For more information, or if you want to

run the code yourself, follow the README instructions on GitHub (<https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/housingprices-ml-sample-solution>). The model metadata is included in form of the machine readable fair4ml file *fair4ml_model_metadata.json* (https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/records/vc0z7-8zt24/files/fair4ml_model_metadata.json?download=1).

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Primarily students and professors in the context of lecture exercises as a sample solution model. The general public might also be interested, since the ames housing dataset is a well know dataset used to tech machine learning.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The filenames are in snake case (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snake_case). There is no real naming convention needed, since only 3 files will be produced and their names are self explanatory. There will be only one version of the endproduct. If someone wants to reproduce the data, he/she can do so themselves easily via the source code on GitHub <https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/housingprices-ml-sample-solution>

To reuse the model, reproduce the experiment or to get more info about the code, one can view the extensive README provided on GitHub <https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/housingprices-ml-sample-solution/blob/master/README.md>. The model itself is described on TUWRD, where it is published. Please see the description: <https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.70124/vc0z7-8zt24>. Furthermore, the record on TUWRD has a domain specific fair4ml machine readable metadata file attached: https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/records/vc0z7-8zt24/files/fair4ml_model_metadata.json?download=1. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We provide open access to all of our data, but it is only allowed to be used in an educational context. For more info, see [Intellectual property rights and rights of use](#).

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	The training data and therefore all derivatives can only be used in an educational context.	2025-04-28	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.70124/vc0z7-8zt24	

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P2	Open	The training data and therefore all derivatives can only be used in an educational context.	2025-04-28	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.70124/vc0z7-8zt24	
P3	Open	The training data and therefore all derivatives can only be used in an educational context.	2025-04-28	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.70124/vc0z7-8zt24	

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: This model was created with Python 3.10, sklearn 1.1.0 and pickle. To reuse the model, open the `ames_housing_prices-model` file with pickle and use sklearn on fitting data to try out the model. For information, see the README and the code that was used to create the model <https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/housingprices-ml-sample-solution>

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you

openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?

- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our model interoperable by providing and describing it in the fair4ml format. The fair4ml file is available at the repository, where we published the model: https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/records/vc0z7-8zt24/files/fair4ml_model_metadata.json?download=1.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make the published model reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme text to the published model in our repository. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. It also covers the rights for reusing the model and graphics associated with it.

Machine readable documentation about the model can be found here https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/records/vc0z7-8zt24/files/fair4ml_model_metadata.json?download=1. Further human readable information about the produced graphics, which show the accuracy of the model, is included in the description on TUWRD: <https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.70124/vc0z7-8zt24>

The following data quality checks will be done: Testing the model on test data and generating graphics that show the absolute error and root squared error.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used

throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

The code that was used to produce the model and graphics is uploaded to GitHub and can be viewed here: <https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/housingprices-ml-sample-solution>.

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR. The work is already uploaded to GitHub and TUWRD and doesn't require much further attention. Possible maintenance work will be done in the context of the lecture, which will use the materials.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Valentin Futterer (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP). The data will be stored on TU Wien servers.

R1 (Ames Housing Prices Training Split), R2 (Ames Housing Prices Validation Split), R3 (Ames Housing Prices Test Split) will be stored on DBRepo.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only
R3	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Research Data	25 years
P2	TU Wien Research Data	25 years
P3	TU Wien Research Data	25 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

Legal restrictions on how data is processed and shared are specified in the Copyright and Usage Policy of the original input data: https://jse.amstat.org/jse_users.htm. The restrictions relate to datasets P1 (ames_housing_prices_model.pkl), P2 (scatter_absolute_error), P3 (scatter_root_squared_error), R1 (Ames Housing Prices Training Split), R2 (Ames Housing Prices Validation Split) and R3 (Ames Housing Prices Test Split). The legal restrictions are based on the following: The training and therefore all derivatives can only be used in an educational context. To obtain more rights, the copyright owner, Dean De Cock has to be contacted.

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Valentin Futterer has access control over the data and the produced model/graphics. Dean De Cock holds the rights to the original data, though it is allowed to use his data in an educational context.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No.